

DISCURSIVE FEATURES OF THE NUMBER OF WORDS IN ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract: Advertising text as a unit of advertising speech is an object of research for experts in various scientific fields. The number of words is an integral element of modern advertising text. In the article, the discursive features of words related to the number of words in advertisements were analyzed.

Keywords: advertising, discourse, vocabulary, pragmatics, text

Among the characteristics of the advertising text as a social phenomenon, it is appropriate to distinguish its perceptual aspects. Social perception is social communication based on emotional cognition, activation of previously acquired knowledge due to social interaction, and "Social perception, that is, the perception of a person by a person depends to a large extent on the level of social intelligence." Social perception is an assessment of a person by another person, and its manifestation in advertising texts is often reflected in the phonetic features of this discourse. Because advertising texts as a product of speech activity, like other types of texts, I.R. As stated by Galperin: "... shows signs of orientation towards a specific goal and pragmatic character."

It is necessary to consider the number phrase as an integral element of the modern advertising text, because numbers attract the addressee and strengthen the effect of advertising on consumers, at the same time, when talking about the events of social life, numbers express the text more clearly than facts: *Chococream, the number **one** chocolate paste in Uzbekistan, is the choice of **millions**.* In advertising texts, the number of words also has its role and place. "Researchers of advertising texts often do not pay enough attention to the pragmatic features of the use of numbers used in the text, taking into account the lexical, syntactic and stylistic

features of the advertising text."

Therefore, the main purpose of numbers used in advertising texts is to reflect objective and unbiased information. At the same time, when interpreting the background information of communicators (their feelings, views, attitudes, values, etc.) in communication, numbers in a certain context serve as a source of speech expression: *Samsung Galaxy S7 will be fully charged in 30 minutes.*

The frequency of using the number word group is a very small percentage of all lexical units in the advertising text. "Because oversaturation of the text with facts made with the help of numbers makes the reader tired." An advertisement in the language of merchants should show proof of the quoted amount, not guesswork: *Don't miss out on the best moments because of a cough, Lozalvan is a three-way anti-cough: it thins phlegm, clears the airways, and protects the lungs. Lazolvan - the best moments are with you. As proof of the three-fold nature of this example: it thins phlegm, clears the respiratory tract, and protects the lungs.* An advertising message "must stand out in a stream of messages of the same type, so very often the quantitative aspect of this information is taken into account."

The use of numbers in the advertising text helps the reader and the advertiser achieve their marketing goals by using numbers related to the author's desire to provide objective and reliable information and attract attention. For example: Duracell batteries: last 10 times longer! Or "Rolton": 3 times cheaper - 100 times tastier!

Small "tricks" with the participation of numbers are also used by text authors and producers in advertising texts to attract economically limited attention. As an example, we can show the following in the text of advertisements of Korzinka supermarkets: 1 kg of beef in Korzinka stores is 69,990 soums. We can see the economic trick here in the price of the product. In the markets, 1 kg of beef costs 70,000 soums.

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